

A novel UHPLC method for quantitative analysis of five anthraquinone derivatives in *Asphodeline* plant extracts

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Abstract

A reverse-phase ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) method was established in this study for the simultaneous determination of five anthraquinones in extracts of *Asphodeline* species. A gradient program was used for chromatographic separation of the components under investigation. The analytes were separated on a Waters Acquity BEH C18 column with a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The mobile phase, consisting of acetonitrile and water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid, was used to elute the components under study. The compounds were detected at 435 nm. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines with respect to specificity, precision, linearity, and robustness. The proposed method was found to be convenient, reliable, and accurate for the quantitative determination of the described anthraquinones in *Asphodeline* species.

Keywords

Asphodeline, anthraquinones, UHPLC method, validation

Introduction

The genus *Asphodeline* Rchb. (Asphodelaceae) includes about seventeen perennial, grass-like flowering species distributed across southeastern Europe, the eastern Mediterranean, Krym, the northern and Transcaucasus regions, western Asia, and northern Africa. Members of the *Asphodeline* genus have been traditionally used in folk medicine and culinary practices (Locatelli et al. 2018). The plants of the genus *Asphodeline* Rchb. are renowned for containing bioactive anthraquinones with antitumor, antioxidant, antifungal, antibacterial,

antiviral, purgative, and other health-beneficial properties (Wang et al. 2021; Mantareva et al. 2024). However, some recent articles describing the toxicity of plants containing anthraquinones and their derivatives, especially side liver effects, have been published (Hudson et al. 2018; Yang et al. 2018). In an earlier investigation, we described the dual biological potential of the dry root extract of *Asphodeline lutea* (L.) Rchb. (AsLuE). The extract exhibited mild hepatotoxic effects and moderate pro-oxidant activity, likely linked to its anthraquinone constituents. Our findings indicated that AsLuE contained a higher total level of anthraquinone derivatives

than those typically found in vegetables commonly consumed in the human diet (Mueller et al. 1999). The *in vivo* analysis of AsLuE also displayed some toxic effects in Wistar rats related to increased enzyme levels of ALT, ALP, and malondialdehyde quantity and decreased GSH levels without affecting the activity of the antioxidant enzymes GPx, GR, and GST (Lazarova et al. 2016). Conversely, the antioxidant and hepatoprotective properties of AsLuE were also observed in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models of CCl₄-induced liver damage, where the extract restored all evaluated parameters to normal levels. In addition, AsLuE maintained the reduced cytochrome P450 content and EMND activity while having no effect on AH activity (Lazarova et al. 2016). These hepatoprotective and antioxidant effects can be explained by the high amount of caffeic acid and flavonoids as well as by metabolic interaction, prohibiting the production of CCl₄ toxic metabolites (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2018).

There is conflicting evidence in the literature regarding the benefits and potential risks of using wild edible plants, food products, and supplements containing hydroxyanthracene derivatives (HADs) such as anthraquinones. Studies on the pharmacological properties and safety of HADs in different plant species are extremely lacking (Xu et al. 2022). Additional toxicological studies and development of reliable methods for the analysis of target compounds in plant extracts and marketed products are needed (Ekor 2013).

Monitoring the main components, especially anthraquinones, in *Asphodeline* species is essential for assessing the safety of consumption of this edible plant. Therefore, the development of a simple, accurate, and reliable analytical method is crucial for its quality control.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and reagents

The compounds aloe-emodin, rhein, emodin, chrysophanol, and physcion (with HPLC purity \geq 98) were sourced from LGC Standards (Teddington, UK). Formic acid and acetonitrile were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Ultrapure water was produced using a Milli-Q Millipore Water Purification System (Bedford, MA, USA). All other chemicals used were of the highest purity available within the laboratory.

Plant material and sample preparation

The *Asphodeline lutea* roots were gathered near the town of Pernik, Bulgaria (42°29'35.15"N, 23°8'7.25"E). The *Asphodeline taurica* roots were collected from Slavyanka Mts (41°24'37.86"N, 23°39'31.15"E). The voucher specimens were preserved at the National Herbarium of the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. The samples were prepared according to the procedure described by Lazarova et al. (2016)

with modifications. Finally, 5 μ L of the sample were injected into the UHPLC system.

Preparation of standard solutions

A solution of each of the five standards was initially prepared at a concentration of 1 mg/mL in methanol. Working mixtures at concentrations of 1, 12.5, 25, 50, and 100 μ g/mL were generated by dilution of a mixed stock solution at 1 mg/mL. Calibration curves were constructed by analyzing freshly prepared standard solutions in triplicate and using a weighted linear least squares regression equation. The concentrations were determined by interpolating the analyte peak areas against the calibration curve. All quantifications were carried out by measuring absorbance at 435 nm.

UHPLC study of anthraquinones

An anthraquinone quantification was conducted using a Dionex UltiMate 3000 RSLC UHPLC system (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Chromatographic separation was achieved through gradient elution at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min on a Waters Acquity BEH C18 column (50 mm \times 2.1 mm internal diameter, 1.7 μ m particle size). The mobile phase, composed of acetonitrile and water with 0.1% (v/v) formic acid, facilitated the elution of the analytes. The gradient conditions were set as follows: 0 min/45% B, 1 min/45% B, 8 min/63% B, 9 min/90% B, 13 min/90% B, 13.1 min/45% B, 15 min/45% B (see Table 1). A 5 μ L injection volume was used, and the column temperature was maintained at 30 °C. Analyte detection was performed at 435 nm, and data processing was carried out with Chromeleon 7.2 software.

Table 1. The mobile phase gradient.

Time (min)	A (%)	B (%)
0	55	45
1	55	45
8	37	63
9	10	90
13	10	90
13.1	55	45
15	55	45

Validation of the method

Validation of the developed method was performed according to the recommendations of the International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH) guideline (ICH 2005). Because the effectiveness of extraction was outside the scope of this study, the recovery was not evaluated.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses were performed using SigmaPlot 12.0 (Systat Software, USA) and Excel software. All measurements were made in triplicate, and the data were presented as mean \pm standard errors.

Results and discussion

Optimization of chromatographic conditions

Chromatographic parameters were optimized to improve peak shape, enhance sensitivity, and reduce analysis time for the simultaneous measurement of five anthraquinones. Various mobile phase compositions were tested to achieve optimal detection, sensitivity, and separation efficiency. Different combinations of methanol–water and acetonitrile–water systems, supplemented with varying concentrations of additives such as formic acid and phosphoric acid, were evaluated. A 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile–0.1% formic acid in water system was found to produce the best chromatographic separation. Subsequently, the gradient elution approach was preferred and optimized. Optimal

separation was accomplished using a Waters Acquity BEH C18 column (50 mm x 2.1 mm i.d., 1.7 μ m) with a gradient program: 0–1 min, 45% B; 1–8 min, 45–63% B; 8–9 min, 63–90% B; 9–13 min, 90% B; 13–13.1 min, 90–45% B; 13.1–15 min, 45% B. The post-run time was 4 min at 45% B to re-equilibrate the column. The flow rate of 0.3 mL/min and the column temperature of 30 °C were preferred. Detection for quantitative analysis was performed at 435 nm.

Figure of merits

- Specificity

The specificity was demonstrated by running a blank solution, standard, and sample (Fig. 1). The column efficiency and peak symmetry for the standard compounds were assessed in accordance with ICH guidelines.

Figure 1. A chromatogram of the blank sample, standard mixed solution, *Asphodeline lutea* sample, and *Asphodeline taurica* sample.

- Linearity

Linearity was assessed by analyzing five known concentrations of the mixed standards solution ranging from 1 to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, with each concentration injected six times. Calibration curves for each anthraquinone were generated by plotting the peak areas against their respective concentrations (Fig. 2). The correlation coefficients, calculated using linear regression, were all greater than 0.99 (Table 2), indicating excellent linearity.

Figure 2. Standard calibration curves of aloe-emodin, rhein, emodin, chrysophanol, and physcion in the range of 1 to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Table 2. The linear equations, correlation coefficients, LODs, and LOQs for anthraquinones under investigation.

Analyte	Linearity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Regression equation ($y = ax + b$)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Aloe-emodin	1–100	$y = 0.2347x + 0.0869$	0.9981	0.03	0.10
Rhein	1–100	$y = 0.1420x + 0.1113$	0.9975	0.06	0.17
Emodin	1–100	$y = 0.2457x - 0.1954$	0.9975	0.07	0.22
Chrysophanol	1–100	$y = 0.5964x - 0.5090$	0.9974	0.05	0.15
Physcion	1–100	$y = 0.0634x - 0.0267$	0.9980	0.08	0.25

- LOD and LOQ

The limit of quantification (LOQ) represents the smallest concentration of an analyte in a sample that can be measured with acceptable accuracy and precision. In contrast, the limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantitatively defined. The LOD and LOQ were calculated using the following equations after injection of standard solutions at low concentrations: $\text{LOQ} = 10\text{SD}/\text{Sl}$ and $\text{LOD} = 3\text{SD}/\text{Sl}$, where SD is the standard deviation of the response and Sl is the slope of the calibration curve.

- Precision

Method precision was evaluated by assessing repeatability as well as inter-day and intra-day precision to ensure consistent performance. The intraday and interday

precision tests were performed with a mixed standard solution of 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in six replicates. The inter-day precision was analyzed by different analysts. Peak area was evaluated, and the results for precision were determined as the percentage relative standard deviation (% RSD) (Table 3).

- Robustness

The robustness of the UHPLC method was evaluated based on the optimized conditions, considering slight

Table 3. Repeatability and reproducibility of the analytical method.

Analyte	Repeatability (n = 6)		Reproducibility (n = 6)	
	Mean ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	RSD (%)	Mean ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	RSD (%)
Aloe-emodin	51.11	0.27	46.77	3.03
Rhein	49.89	0.27	46.44	4.01
Emodin	48.96	0.44	44.54	2.67
Chrysophanol	48.34	0.43	43.65	5.34
Physcion	48.99	0.29	45.98	5.11

and acceptable variations in key parameters to ensure consistent performance. The estimated parameters were mobile phase composition (0.1%, 0.4%, and 0.7% formic acid) and wavelength (430 nm, 435 nm, and 440 nm). Retention times and peak areas were verified for ruggedness by injecting the standard mixture at 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (Table 4).

Table 4. Robustness of the analytical method.

Compound	Retention times \pm SD						Peaks area \pm SD		
	0.1% FA	0.4% FA	0.7% FA	0.1% FA	0.4% FA	0.7% FA	430 nm	435 nm	440 nm
Aloe-emodin	3.54 \pm 0.03	3.54 \pm 0.02	3.49 \pm 0.02	9.5628 \pm 0.05	9.0370 \pm 0.10	9.5716 \pm 0.11	9.1164 \pm 0.19	9.5628 \pm 0.05	8.6743 \pm 0.07
Rhein	4.92 \pm 0.03	4.91 \pm 0.03	4.83 \pm 0.02	6.1067 \pm 0.07	5.8301 \pm 0.18	6.3071 \pm 0.10	6.0492 \pm 0.07	6.1067 \pm 0.07	5.7530 \pm 0.05
Emodin	9.72 \pm 0.02	9.73 \pm 0.02	9.66 \pm 0.00	10.3355 \pm 0.17	10.7673 \pm 0.02	11.1029 \pm 0.18	10.7574 \pm 0.09	10.3355 \pm 0.17	10.8256 \pm 0.17
Chrysophanol	9.97 \pm 0.02	9.98 \pm 0.01	9.89 \pm 0.01	19.1168 \pm 0.19	18.6537 \pm 0.08	18.8842 \pm 0.18	18.4507 \pm 0.22	19.1168 \pm 0.19	17.5724 \pm 0.19
Physcion	11.78 \pm 0.01	11.78 \pm 0.01	11.73 \pm 0.00	1.7798 \pm 0.04	1.8194 \pm 0.03	1.8106 \pm 0.01	1.7093 \pm 0.15	1.7798 \pm 0.04	1.7380 \pm 0.16

Two samples of *Asphodeline lutea* and *Asphodeline taurica* roots were analyzed using the method developed above. The content of each of the five anthraquinones in the analyzed samples was calculated according to the dry material (Table 5).

Table 5. The anthraquinone content in *Asphodeline lutea* and *Asphodeline taurica* root extracts.

Analyte	<i>Asphodeline lutea</i>	<i>Asphodeline taurica</i>
	Content $\mu\text{g/g}$ (n = 3)	Content $\mu\text{g/g}$ (n = 3)
Aloe-emodin	22.13 \pm 0.22	27.63 \pm 0.31
Rhein	22.73 \pm 0.27	21.21 \pm 0.18
Emodin	Not detected	Not detected
Chrysophanol	37.90 \pm 0.20	38.26 \pm 0.11
Physcion	Not detected	3.76 \pm 0.12

Conclusion

A reverse-phase ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) technique was successfully developed and thoroughly validated for the simultaneous quantification of five key anthraquinones – aloe-emodin, rhein, emodin, chrysophanol, and physcion – in different species of *Asphodeline*. The method proved to be straightforward, dependable, precise, and efficient, significantly reducing the time required for analysis while maintaining high accuracy. Given its robustness and sensitivity, this UHPLC method is well suited for routine monitoring and quality control assessments of plant materials and their derived products containing the targeted anthraquinones, thereby ensuring both their consistency and safety for use.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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